

Concerning an Heuristic Point of View on the Origin of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle

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Abstract

Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle is fundamental in Quantum Mechanics. The spread in wavelength corresponds to the spread in momentum. Our theoretical calculation shows, precisely determines a particle's position is, so less precise is its momentum. Planck's mass m_p is the mass after which the quantum effects of gravity become significant. In this paper, we have presented a new heuristic view of Planck's units. By using Planck's units, we will redefine the validity of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle. Relationship between Planck's Length, Planck's Time and Planck's Mass results in the origin of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle. The laws of Quantum Mechanics and Quantum Field theory permits us to quantise the energy of photons. We will raise the conjecture (the purport of which will be called the theory of Quantisation of Space and Time) **that Space and Time are physical entities having Space Quanta –Spacion and Time Quanta –Timion. Time and Space itself is a physical entity which have the lowest limits. The fabric of space-time is a 4-dimensional Tesseract, where 3 dimensions of Space are fixed and 4th Dimension, time is constantly projecting the universe in the forward direction. Space-Time is constantly evolving, the Time quanta and Space quanta are the building blocks of empty space.**

1. Introduction of Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle

Heisenberg uncertainty is an inherent phenomenon, as far as quantum mechanics is concerned. A quantum particle's precise position and momentum cannot be determined simultaneously. However, in classical physics, a particle's position and momentum may both be precisely measured at the same time and are independent of one another. Imagine that we are holding the end of a long rope. By rhythmically shaking the rope up and down, we can create a wave on the rope (Figure 1.1). You would likely consider it odd if someone asked you, "Exactly where is the wave on the rope?" Since the wave is not precisely situated anyplace. It covers a 50-foot area. On the other hand, if he inquires, "What is a wave's wavelength?" "You could respond to him rationally. It seems to be 6 feet.

Figure 1.1: A wave with a well-defined wavelength but ill-defined position (it is spread over 50 feet)

As an alternative, if you suddenly jerked the rope (Figure 1.2), you would cause a rather narrow bump to travel below the line. Continuing to look at the initial query, "Exactly where is the wave on the rope?" It is evident that this time, we are certain of the wave's exact position. However, what about looking at the second query, "What is the wavelength of wave on the rope?" It seems absurd. Even so, it is not cyclical. So how can you give it a wavelength? When the wave is reasonably well localised and the wavelength is reasonably well defined, we can sketch intermediate examples. However, there must be a trade-off in this situation: When a wave position is more accurate, its momentum is less precise, and vice versa.

Figure 1.2: Wave on the rope with a well-defined position but ill-defined wavelength.

Naturally, every wave phenomenon is affected by this event, hence the quantum mechanical wave function is specifically affected. The De-Broglie formula tells us that in quantum mechanics, wavelength and particle momentum are connected. [1] Where p stands for the particle's momentum, λ for the wave's wavelength, h for Planck's constant, and \hbar for the reduced Planck's constant.

$$p = \frac{h}{\lambda} = \frac{2\pi\hbar}{\lambda}$$

Thus, we can see that the spread in wavelength and the spread in momentum are related, and in general, our research indicates that the more accurately a particle's position is known, the less precisely its momentum is known. Qualitatively

$$\delta_x \delta_p \geq \hbar$$

Where δ_x represents positional uncertainty and δ_p represents momentum uncertainty. This is the well-known uncertainty principle of Heisenberg. It asserts that a particle's position and momentum cannot be specified simultaneously with arbitrary accuracy and that the sum of their respective degrees of uncertainty is always larger than a quantity of order \hbar . Suppose $\Psi(x, t)$ is an one-dimensional wave packet made up of the superposition of plane waves:

$$\Psi(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A(k) e^{i(kx - \omega t)} dk$$

Where $A(k)$ determines the amplitude and ω , the angular frequency. It is obvious that we must forgo the constraint that the particle has a precisely specified momentum in order to represent a free particle by a wave packet. The inverse Fourier transform of $\Psi(x, t)$ yields the amplitude function $A(k)$

$$A(k)e^{-i\omega t} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Psi(x, t)e^{-ikx} dx$$

$$A(k) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Psi(x, t)e^{-i(kx-\omega t)} dx$$

We must now localise the wave packet because we want it to describe a particle. In order to do this, we suppose that $A(k)$ is centred on a specific number, $k=k_0$ and that it quickly decreases to zero outside of an interval $(k_0 - \frac{\Delta k}{2}, k_0 + \frac{\Delta k}{2})$, where Δk is small. Then,

$$\Psi(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{k_0 - \frac{\Delta k}{2}}^{k_0 + \frac{\Delta k}{2}} A(k)e^{i(kx-\omega t)} dk$$

To expand it in a Taylor series about k_0 , we additionally suppose that $\omega(k)$ varies slowly with k :

$$\omega(k) = \omega(k_0) + (k - k_0) \left(\frac{d\omega}{dk} \right)_{k=k_0} + \frac{1}{2} (k - k_0)^2 \left(\frac{d^2\omega}{dk^2} \right)_{k=k_0} + \dots$$

Considering values of k that are near to k_0 while ignoring second and higher-order terms, and placing $\omega(k_0) = \omega_0$, we obtain

$$\Psi(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\Delta k} A(k) \exp \left[i \left\{ (k - k_0)x + k_0x - \omega_0 t - (k - k_0)t \frac{d\omega}{dk} \right\} \right] dk$$

$$= f(x, t) e^{i(k_0x - \omega_0 t)}$$

Where

$$f(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\Delta k} A(k) \exp \left[i \left(x - \frac{d\omega}{dk} t \right) (k - k_0) \right] dk$$

The equation above demonstrates that the wave function $\Psi(x, t)$ is a wave with a wavelength of $2\pi/k$ and a frequency of ω . The only way the envelope is dependent on x and t is via the combination $\frac{d\omega}{dk} t$. As a result, it symbolises a wave packet that moves at the group velocity.

$$v_g = \frac{d\omega}{dk}$$

We draw attention to a fascinating and crucial general characteristic of wave packets. If a wave packet's spatial extent is Δx and its wave number range is Δk , then this is always the case.

$$\Delta x \Delta k \geq 1$$

Reciprocity relation is the name of the equation above. As a result, it is impossible to reduce the "width" of both Δx and Δk . The range of wave numbers in a wave packet's Fourier decomposition increases with decreasing spatial extent of the wave packet and vice versa. This characteristic of wave packets generally has profound ramifications for quantum mechanics. If a wave packet represents a particle, anywhere in the region where the amplitude of the wave function $\Psi(x, t)$ is nonzero is where the particle can be discovered. As a result, the particle's position within the wave packet's width is uncertain. We will review the reciprocity relationship between the k-space wave function and the width in x-space:

$$\Delta x \Delta k \geq 1$$

By applying the relation $\hbar k = p$, where p is momentum and k is the wavenumber, we obtain

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar$$

2. On the limit of the smallest possible Time and distance in Space

2.1. On the origin of the Speed of light

Speed of light C is the cosmic limit of velocity in the universe. The Special Theory of Relativity predicts that nothing can travel faster than the speed of light in free space.

$$\Delta x = c \times \Delta t$$

Here Δx is the distance travelled by light and Δt is the time passed during the travelling of this distance. We have an inequality

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \leq c$$

A set of measurements known as Planck's units is only used in particle physics and physical cosmology. They are defined in terms of four fundamental physical constants, and when written in terms of these units, the Boltzmann constant k_b , the reduced Planck's constant \hbar , the gravitational constant G , and the speed of light c , all equals one. Because the defining of these units is based on natural features, particularly those of free space, as opposed to a selection of prototype objects, as was the case with Max Planck's original 1899 proposal, they are a system of natural units. The study of unifying theories like quantum gravity can benefit from them.

Name	Dimension	Expression	Value (SI units)
Planck Length	Length (L)	$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}$	$1.616255(18) \times 10^{-35}$ m [3]
Planck Mass	Mass (M)	$m_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}}$	$2.176434(24) \times 10^{-8}$ kg [4]

Planck Time	Time (T)	$t_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}}$	$5.391247(60) \times 10^{-44} \text{ s [5]}$
Planck Temperature	Temperature (θ)	$T_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{G k_B^2}}$	$1.416784(16) \times 10^{32} \text{ K [6]}$

Table 1.1. Modern values for Planck's original choice of quantities, the numbers in brackets represent the decimal places where the values are uncertain.

The results of a previous investigation on the General theory of relativity lead to the very interesting conclusion that; Speed of light –C is the highest possible speed limit in free space. This conclusion leads me to put forward the conjecture that:

The lowest possible distance in free space is Planck's length (l_P) and the smallest possible time in the free space of the universe is Planck's Time (t_P)

After substituting the value of Planck's length, $\Delta x = l_P$ and Planck's Time, $\Delta t = t_P$ in the inequality given below, we come to an interesting result.

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \leq c$$

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \leq \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}}}$$

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \leq c \leq 2.99792,458 \text{ m/s}$$

The maximum velocity of the particle in the empty space is Planck's length divided by Planck's time. This is the natural construction of space-time where space and time itself limit the fastest velocity in the universe.

2.2. On Quantisation of Time and lowest value of Time Possible

After rearranging the terms in the above inequality we get another interesting result;

$$\frac{\Delta x}{c} \leq \Delta t$$

We want to find the limit of time, i.e. the lowest value of time possible in this free space. For that we have to enter, the lowest value of distance travelled in the free space of this universe and the highest value of speed, in the free space of the universe, i.e. the lowest value of the numerator and highest value of the denominator after substituting these values, we get

$$\frac{\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}}{c} \leq \Delta t$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}} \leq \Delta t$$

Hence the change in time is always greater than Planck's time. When we divide, the smallest possible distance in free space in the universe, and the smallest possible time in the universe we get the speed of light in free space.

2.3. On Quantisation of Space and lowest possible distance

We also have from above inequality

$$\Delta x \leq c \Delta t$$

$$\Delta x \leq c \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}}$$

Hence by substituting values in the above equation, we get the smallest value of distance possible in the free space. We propose that universe is fabricated with 4-dimensional space-time. Where Space itself is composed of three-dimensional Space. We define a new word, Spacion for Quanta of distance in space. Spacion is the smallest possible length of the distance in the universe. It is the fabric of this cosmos and its value is Planck's length and its dimension is of length. We define Timion as the quanta of Time and its value is equal to Planck's Time and the dimension is time. Timion and Spacion are the fabric of this universe, they are coupled to form 4-dimensional space-time. Where space is fixed and time is constantly emerging as the universe evolves. Time is evolving and passing at the frame rate of Timion. Space and Time

are not continuous. Quantum Mechanics proves that the energy of the photon is quantised. Similarly, Distance travelled and time passed are quantised. Qualitatively;

$$\text{Distance} = n l_p$$

Distance is the total distance travelled in the universe, l_p is Planck's distance and n is the integer similar to the time we have qualitatively;

$$\text{Time Passed} = n t_p$$

Total time passed is the total time passed in the universe, t_p is Planck's time and n is an integer.

3. On the origin of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle

Quantum Mechanics predicts empty space is not empty, quantum fluctuation is inherent in space. The General Theory of Relativity describes the model of space-time. In the previous section we have quantised, the distance in free space and time. It is mathematically possible to derive the uncertainty relation from the wave packet. We are compelled to accept them because we must resolve the wave-particle duality of matter. These relationships are specific illustrations of Heisenberg's 1927 formulation of the uncertainty principle. He understood it to be a fundamental idea that underlies the framework of quantum mechanics. The guiding idea is as follows:

The Uncertainty Principle

The exact values of both members of some pairs of a system's dynamical variables cannot be specified at the same time. In the traditional Hamiltonian meaning, these variables—which are often referred to as complementary variables—are canonically conjugate with one another. The product of the two variables' respective uncertainty is at least of the order of \hbar .

Typical instances of complimentary variables include: a particle's Δx Cartesian coordinate and its corresponding momentum (Δp). A particle's energy and measured time. It is important to remember that the uncertainty principle's restriction on measurement has nothing to do with the experimental errors that are present during real measurement. Furthermore, because it is so small, the uncertainty principle only applies to systems with atomic-scale dimensions. Both material particles and photons are subjected to the uncertainty principle. Qualitatively, in accordance with the uncertainty principle;

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar$$

Where Δx represents the particle's uncertain position and Δp represents the particle's uncertain momentum. Taken together with the equation's expansion, the left-hand side of the one above, yields the result:

$$\Delta x m \Delta v \geq \hbar$$

$$\Delta x m \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \geq \hbar$$

After substituting the value of Spacion, Timion and Planck's mass in the above equation and equating to a constant k, we get

$$l_p m_p \frac{l_p}{t_p} = k$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}}} = k$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}}} = \hbar$$

When we calculate the value of k, it turns out to be \hbar ! It's a miracle. Let's apply the initial inequality we get.

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \leq c$$

$$\frac{\hbar}{\Delta x m} \leq c \leq \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t}$$

When we rearrange the above equation we get the Heisenberg's uncertainty relation

$$\Delta x m \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \geq \hbar$$

Based on the above result we put forward a conjecture that; **the universe itself has the smallest limit of time (Timion), the smallest limit of distance (Spacion) and the smallest limit of mass (Planck's mass). Planck's mass is the limit of validity of the mass of an object, where**

the uncertainty principle holds correct. When the mass is above Planck's mass, classical mechanics will dominate. We can precisely determine simultaneously the value of both uncertainty in position and uncertainty in momentum. Qualitatively

$$\Delta x \ m \ \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \geq \hbar$$

Then after substituting the value of Planck's length, and Planck's time we get an inequality

$$m \geq \frac{\hbar \ t_p}{l_p^2}$$

This m comes out to be the Planck's mass. We define this mass limit as the fundamental unit of mass above which classical mechanics will dominate, we will call this mass limit as Masion. The universe itself has a 4-dimensional Tesseract, where the limit of Time, Space and mass is inherent in any physical system. By using the Heisenberg uncertainty principle let's calculate the limit of distance. Rearranging the above equation mathematically we come to an interesting conclusion;

$$l_p \geq \sqrt{\frac{\hbar t_p}{m_p}}$$

This distance comes out to be the Planck's length, hence we prove that the smallest possible distance is Spacion. Space and Time are coupled, and both exist simultaneously. Space is equivalent to time. Disturbance in space results in the disturbance of time. I will explain this in my later work.

4. On the origin of Uncertainty in Energy and Time

Scientists refer to energy as the ability to perform labour. Modern civilisation is made possible by the discovery of how to change energy from one form to another and use it to complete activities. $E=hv$, where E is the particle's energy, h is Planck's constant, and v is the particle's frequency, which is how the energy of a photon is quantized in quantum physics. We suggest that time and energy are both a part of the structure of space. Energy may be changed into time and vice versa. We have a mathematically stated uncertainty connection for time and energy;

$$\Delta E \Delta t \geq \hbar$$

Here ΔE refers to uncertainty in energy and Δt is uncertainty in time. Let's take the left-hand side equation and substitute the value of Timion, Spacion and Masion. We have from Einstein's energy-mass equivalence.

$$\Delta E = m_p c^2$$

After substituting this value in the left-hand side of the uncertainty relation and equate to a constant k , we get

$$m_p c^2 t_p = k$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}} c^2 \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}} = \hbar$$

Miracle! Again we get \hbar in this result after entering the lowest value of mass and the value of Timion, we again get, reduced Planck's constant \hbar . This result intends me to put forward a conjecture that; Time and Energy are interconnected and space is interconnected with time. This implies Space, Time and Energy are interconnected.

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m_p t_p}}$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{m_p t_p}} \leq c \leq \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t}$$

After rearranging the equation we get an Uncertainty relation. Heisenberg's uncertainty principle is the fundamental principle of nature, it is originating because of the interaction of space, time and energy. Spacion, Timion, and Masion results in Heisenberg Uncertainty.

5. On Quantisation of mass and smallest possible mass of the Black holes

We have used the value of mass as Planck's mass, let's start by thinking about it to define a location in a gravitational field with perfect precision, in other words, what it means to talk about very tiny chunks in the fabric of space. In order to measure a location in space, say the location of the particle, you need to interact with it. You would typically do that by bouncing a photon or other particle off the object. The more precisely you want to measure position the higher the energy of that interaction. That's why we use electron microscopes or X-rays or even gamma rays to take the image of extremely small things. So let's say we shoot a particle with a beam from a particle accelerator to measure its location with extreme precision. Heisenberg's uncertainty principle tells us the minimum energy of our beam for a given precision. It turns out that to measure a position to an accuracy better than a Planck length $1.616255(18) \times 10^{-35}$ m the amount of energy you would need to put into that region of space would make a tiny black hole with an event horizon, 2 times the Planck length in radius. Try to measure more precisely and you need more energy which means you make an even larger black hole, so general relativity and Heisenberg's principle says, it's impossible to measure a length smaller than the Planck's length. The physical quantity known as the Schwarzschild radius, also known as the gravitational radius, is used to define the Schwarzschild black hole's event horizon in the Schwarzschild solution to the Einstein's field equations. It is a distinctive radius connected to any mass quantity. After German astronomer Karl Schwarzschild, who derived this precise general relativity solution in 1916, the Schwarzschild radius was called. The Schwarzschild radius is given as;

$$r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$$

After substituting the value of Planck's mass, $m_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}}$ in the above equation we get

$$r_s = 2 \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}}$$

We get radius as 2 times the Planck's length. **We propose mass of the black hole is quantised and is equal to n times the Planck's mass. The smallest possible black hole will have a mass equal to Planck's mass and the radius will be 2 times the Planck's length.**

Results and Discussion

It's interesting to notice that the accurate Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle emerges from a qualitative debate utilising Planck's length, mass, and time. The hydrogen atom's ground-state energy and radius are determined by the uncertainty principle. It's crucial to remember that an atom's total energy has a minimum value that is consistent with the uncertainty principle. The reason why atoms are stable and do not collapse is likewise obvious. To paraphrase from Feynman's Physics Lectures [2].

So we now understand why we do not fall through the floor. As we walk, our shoes with their mass of atoms push against the floor with their mass of atoms. In order to squash the atoms close together, the electron would be confined to a smaller space, and by the uncertainty principle, their momenta would have to be higher on the average, and that means high energy; the resistance to atomic compression is a quantum mechanical effect and not a classical effect [2]

Space Quanta – Spacion is the smallest possible distance in free space, and Quanta of Time – Timion is the smallest possible Time in the universe. When we attempt to measure the position and the momentum simultaneously, the lowest value of Spacion or Timion exceeds and results in $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar$. Uncertainty principles arise due to the inherent property of space and time, they are not characterised by any phenomenon. When the special combination of Gravitational constant $-G$, Speed of light in free space c , and reduced Planck's- \hbar are employed then we get the value of Spacion, Timion and Masion. Further, these values result in the Uncertainty Principle.

Summary and conclusion

The general theory of Relativity limits the highest value of the velocity of any particle, and the speed of light in free space. According to Quantum mechanics, we can only find the probability of measured distance and measured momentum, nothing is certain. Quantum mechanics is the world of probability. This arises because of the limit present in the value of space, time and mass. So In this paper, we emphasise with having the lowest possible value of time, the lowest possible value of length and the highest value of mass up to which the Heisenberg Uncertainty principle holds correct. We defined Timion as Quanta of time having time equal to Planck's time. We defined Spacion as the lowest value of distance in free space and is equal to Planck's length. There is a natural slit in the universe whose spread is limited to the lowest value possible of distance (Spacion). There is one more slit of time whose spread is limited to the lowest

possible time (Timion). Minimum Spread in these slits is characterised by fundamental constants in nature. I.e. c (Speed of light in free space), G (gravitational constant) and \hbar (Reduced Planck's constant). We have taken mass as Planck's mass. It is the highest value of mass for which Heisenberg uncertainty holds correct. It is the mass of the smallest Black hole. When Mass is above Planck's mass, classical physics will dominate and the uncertainty principle will be violated for a classical particle. We can find precise position and momentum simultaneously. Then we derived Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle with the help of these constants. We conclude that there is a limit to every inherent property of the universe. These limits are imposed by different natural constants present in the universe mentioned earlier. I will discuss more about them in my future work.

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